

ML2++ in Practice: A Use-Case-Aware Study of Modeling Effort and Usability for Forecasting-Enabled IoT/CPS

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Abstract

Building a forecasting-enabled IoT/CPS application is more than a modeling problem: the forecast must be prepared, trained, evaluated, visualized, and wired back into alerts, dashboards, and runtime decisions, and that work is usually spread across scripts, notebooks, and hand-written integration code. ML2++, a model-driven framework introduced in recent work, pulls these concerns into a single model and generates the executable pipeline from it. What has been missing is evidence that this pays off in practice. We provide that evidence from three angles: an artifact-based technical validation across three forecasting use cases (river-flow, smart-home energy, and solar power); a three-stage user study comparing manual Python development, IoT-template reuse, and textual ML2++ modeling against a realistic baseline that includes both forecasting code and IoT integration; and a complementary study of the graphical (Sirius-Web) editor against textual ML2. Because the sample is small and heterogeneous, we report results descriptively. Of the five participants who completed the Stage-3 task, four took less time than the combined baseline and one slightly more; three further participants finished only partially, so their lower times are reported separately as weaker evidence rather than clean reductions. The graphical editor cut manual code, syntax errors, and debugging time while improving satisfaction. The clearest lesson is not that effort disappears but that it *moves*: from writing and gluing code toward configuring the model, understanding the language, and authoring the model instance. We turn this into a concrete research direction.

CCS Concepts

• **Software and its engineering** → **Domain specific languages**; **Empirical software validation**; • **Computer systems organization** → **Embedded and cyber-physical systems**; • **Computing methodologies** → **Machine learning**; • **Human-centered computing** → **User studies**.

Keywords

model-driven engineering, empirical evaluation, Internet of Things, time-series forecasting, domain-specific modeling languages, graphical modeling, ML2++

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1 Introduction

Forecasts increasingly act, rather than merely inform. In Internet of Things (IoT) and Cyber-Physical Systems (CPS), a predicted river level can raise a flood alert, a predicted load can switch a home between “safe” and “alert” modes, and a predicted solar yield can shape an operational plan. When a number does that much, its trustworthiness depends on far more than the forecasting algorithm: it depends on whether the data preparation, feature roles, lag windows, horizon, metrics, plots, and runtime bindings were all built under the same assumptions [7, 8, 12].

In everyday practice these assumptions are scattered across notebooks, scripts, and hand-written glue code, so it is often impossible to say whether the prediction a user sees, the metric an experiment reports, and the value the application consumes were produced the same way [3, 8]. Model-Driven Engineering (MDE) offers a way out by making the model the primary artifact and generating the implementation from it [3, 5]. This is a natural fit for IoT/CPS, which already blend architecture, device interaction, data processing, runtime behavior, and machine learning [7, 12].

This is the idea behind ML2++, a model-driven framework, introduced in recent work, that grew out of a longer line of work: DAML methods for smart IoT services [12], a scoping review of MDE for

ML-enabled IoT [11], and ML2+, which brought time-series forecasting into the ML2 modeling layer [9]. ML2++ represents forecasting directly at the model level, including datasets, features, preprocessing, horizons, algorithms, metrics, visualization, and runtime decisions, and generates the executable pipeline, through either a textual or a graphical editor [10]. The framework, its language, and its toolchain have been presented elsewhere. What has *not* been established is the practical question that decides whether such a framework matters: *does modeling a forecasting-enabled IoT/CPS application in ML2++ actually take less effort than building it by hand, and where does the remaining effort go?* Prior work in this line demonstrated expressiveness and code generation, not measured developer effort against a realistic baseline.

This paper answers that question empirically, along three complementary lines of evidence. First, an artifact-based technical validation applies a common protocol to three model instances, covering river-flow, smart-home energy, and solar power, to check that ML2++ can express genuinely different forecasting workflows, generate runnable artifacts, and produce observable evidence such as logs, metrics, plots, predictions, and alerts. Second, a three-stage user study contrasts manual Python development (Stage 1), IoT-template reuse (Stage 2), and textual ML2++ modeling (Stage 3); crucially, the baseline is *Stage 1 plus Stage 2*, because a fair comparison must include both the forecasting code and the IoT integration a non-model-driven developer would still write. Third, a complementary study compares the graphical Sirius-Web editor with textual ML2. These map onto four research questions (RQ1–RQ4) in Section 4.

Our findings are deliberately reported as descriptive evidence rather than statistical proof, because the user sample is small and heterogeneous. Within those limits the picture is consistent and useful: most participants took less time in the ML2++ stage than in the combined baseline. This should be read cautiously, given the fixed stage order and three partial completions (Section 10). The graphical editor reduced hand-written code and debugging while raising satisfaction, and, most informatively, the difficulty that remained was concentrated in *authoring and configuring the model itself*. That single observation shapes both our discussion and a concrete next step. Concretely, the paper (i) frames the evaluation of a forecasting MDE tool as assessing an *evidence chain* from model declarations to generated outputs; (ii) reports a use-case-aware technical validation; (iii) delivers, to our knowledge, one of the first effort comparisons of ML2++ against a realistic non-model-driven baseline; and (iv) adds graphical-editor evidence on code, errors, debugging, learnability, and satisfaction.

2 ML2++ in Brief

Because ML2++ and its toolchain are described in detail elsewhere [10], we recap only what is needed to read the evaluation. ML2++ is a domain-specific modeling language built on the ThingML/ML-Quadrat tradition, including Things, ports, messages, properties, state machines, configurations, instances, and connectors [7], and is extended with a forecasting-oriented *data analytics* construct that groups six concerns: data, preprocessing, time-series configuration, model configuration, evaluation, and visualization.

The point of the language is that forecasting decisions stop being buried in code and become explicit, inspectable model elements: a modeler declares the dataset, features, lag and horizon, algorithm, metrics, and plots (Figure 1), and the generator produces the runnable pipeline. This is not formal verification, but it creates a repeatable chain from specification to generated code and from execution back to evidence. We measure this value *indirectly*, through effort and reported difficulty rather than defect detection, leaving the latter to future work.

As Figure 1 shows, ML2++ offers two ways into the same meta-model. The textual route (Textula, the ML2++ textual editor) supports editing, validation, code generation, and local execution. The graphical route (Sirius-Web) supports form-based authoring, exports an instance model, and runs it server-side through the Orchestrator, which returns logs, metrics, predictions, plots, and alerts. Because both editors share one metamodel, they produce equivalent forecasting workflows, which is what lets us evaluate the two modalities as alternatives rather than as different tools.

3 Related Work

DSLs and MDE for IoT/CPS. Modeling languages such as ThingML and its successor ML-Quadrat generate platform code from architectural and behavioral models of IoT systems [7, 12], establishing the Things/ports/state-machine vocabulary that ML2++ reuses. Our work extends this tradition from system structure and behavior toward data-centric forecasting.

Integrating ML and forecasting into models. DAML-based approaches first brought data analytics and machine learning into model-driven IoT engineering [12]; a scoping review then mapped MDE techniques for ML-enabled IoT and highlighted weak support for data-centric workflows and automation [11]; and ML2+ added time-series forecasting to the ML2 modeling layer [9]. ML2++ continues this line, and, unlike these mostly feasibility-oriented studies, contributes a use-case-aware *effort* evaluation.

Low-code, IoT, and MLOps tools. Web-based graphical frameworks such as Sirius Web enable browser-based modeling [6]; flow-based IoT tools such as Node-RED and StreamPipes support low-code data integration and stream analytics [2, 14]; and MLOps tools such as MLflow, TFX, Kubeflow Pipelines, and SageMaker support tracking, orchestration, deployment, and monitoring [1, 13, 16, 17]. These tools are complementary rather than substitutes for our baseline: they manage flows or lifecycle artifacts, whereas ML2++ studies whether an MDE model can bind IoT/CPS structure, forecasting configuration, plots, and alert behavior into one generated artifact chain.

Empirical evaluation of modeling tools. Empirical, use-case-aware effort comparisons for *forecasting-enabled* IoT/CPS modeling against a realistic non-model-driven baseline remain scarce [11]. This paper targets that gap with a staged, within-participant design and a complementary graphical-editor study; a direct head-to-head comparison with low-code/MLOps systems is left to future work.

Figure 1: The two ML2++ authoring routes over a shared metamodel: a textual route (Textula → validation → code generation → local execution) and a graphical route (Sirius-Web → exported instance model → server-side Orchestrator → generated logs, metrics, predictions, plots, and alerts).

4 Research Design

4.1 What We Evaluate, and What We Deliberately Do Not

Evaluating a model-driven framework can mean many things. We focus on the two questions that decide whether ML2++ is worth adopting in practice: can it *express and generate* real forecasting-enabled IoT/CPS workflows, and does modeling in it *cost less effort* than building the same system by hand? We therefore combine two perspectives. The first is technical feasibility, assessed by constructing three model instances and checking that ML2++ can represent distinct forecasting workflows and generate runnable, runtime-connected artifacts. The second is developer effort and experience, assessed through a staged user study.

We are equally explicit about what is *out of scope*. This paper does not try to identify the most accurate forecasting algorithm, and it does not claim predictive superiority for any model family. The algorithms are vehicles for exercising the framework; the object under study is the *engineering process*, not the forecast quality. Keeping this boundary sharp is what lets us interpret the results cleanly: a long modeling time reflects modeling effort, not a search for the best model.

4.2 Research Questions

The two perspectives refine into four research questions. The first two ask whether the framework does what it promises:

- **RQ1 (Expressiveness)**. Can ML2++ express complete forecasting workflows across representative IoT/CPS domains?
- **RQ2 (Generation & integration)**. Can model-level declarations be transformed into executable artifacts and connected to application-level behavior such as alerting and monitoring?

The next two ask whether the framework helps the people who use it:

- **RQ3 (Effort)**. How does the effort of modeling in ML2++ compare with a realistic non-model-driven baseline?
- **RQ4 (Residual difficulty)**. When developers move from scripts and templates to ML2++, which difficulties remain, and where do they concentrate?

RQ1 and RQ2 are answered by the artifact-based technical validation (Section 5); RQ3 and RQ4 by the staged user study (Sections 6–7). RQ4 is what ultimately gives the paper its practical message, because the location of the remaining difficulty is what future tooling must target.

4.3 A Three-Stage Study

The user study walks the same forecasting task through three increasingly model-driven settings, so that each participant serves as their own reference point. In **Stage 1 (manual Python)** a participant implements the forecasting workflow from scratch: preparing data, engineering features, configuring and training a model, evaluating it, plotting, and debugging. In **Stage 2 (IoT-template reuse)** they take that working forecasting code and fit it into an IoT-oriented execution template, the step that turns an analytics script into something an IoT/CPS application can run. In **Stage 3 (ML2++ modeling)** they instead specify the workflow as an ML2++ model and rely on generated execution support. This staged shape lets us contrast script-centric development, template-based integration, and model-driven development on a like-for-like basis.

4.4 Why the Baseline Is Stage 1 plus Stage 2

The key methodological choice is the baseline. Comparing ML2++ against Stage 1 alone, that is, manual forecasting code, would be

unfair: the deliverable is not a notebook but a forecasting-enabled IoT/CPS application, and a non-ML2++ developer must still integrate the forecasting code into an executable IoT structure, exactly the work Stage 2 captures. Charging ML2++ with both forecasting and integration while crediting the manual route with forecasting only understates the manual cost. We therefore define the realistic non-model-driven baseline as

$$\text{Baseline} = \text{Stage 1} + \text{Stage 2},$$

and compare Stage 3 against it. The question is thus not “is modeling faster than writing a forecasting script?” but the question that actually matters in practice: “is modeling faster than getting from a forecasting requirement to a running IoT/CPS workflow?” Figure 2 summarizes this logic.

4.5 Measures and Analysis

For each stage we record *visible time*, defined as the participant-reported wall-clock minutes spent actively working on a step, excluding clearly separable idle waiting, per workflow step (preprocessing, configuration, training, evaluation, plotting, debugging, and learning), together with task completion, self-reported difficulty per step and per language element, error frequency and clarity, debugging effort, perceived code quality and maintainability, and overall satisfaction. Time was captured through manual activity logs filled per stage/step; no IDE telemetry or screen-recorded timing was used. To keep the deliverable comparable, each participant received the same use-case target checklist for its assigned case: target variable, input features, lag/horizon, metrics, plots, and the alert or monitoring binding expected at the end of the workflow. A Stage 3 task is marked complete only when that functional target was reached; partial runs are therefore reported separately. For Stage 3 we also record the number of DSL lines written. The primary outcome for RQ3 is the within-participant difference between the combined baseline and Stage 3; the difficulty and satisfaction measures feed RQ4.

We analyze the data *descriptively*, and by design rather than by omission. The participants, use cases, model families, and backgrounds are heterogeneous, and the sample is small, so aggregate statistics would imply a precision the study does not have. The strongest and fairest comparison is therefore within a participant, read use case by use case: each person’s combined baseline against their own Stage 3. Cross-participant comparisons are treated cautiously throughout, and any approximate responses are reported as such rather than smoothed over. This stance is what keeps the conclusions defensible despite the small sample, and it is revisited in Section 10.

5 Technical Validation Through Use Cases

Before asking whether ML2++ saves effort, we first check whether it can carry the required engineering work from a model to runnable outputs. To avoid presenting the three use cases as illustrative examples only, we use a common artifact-based validation protocol. For each case we check whether ML2++ can: (i) express the required data, preprocessing, forecasting, evaluation, visualization, and prediction-binding concerns at the model level; (ii) generate

Table 1: Artifact-based technical validation across the three ML2++ use cases.

Use case	Forecasting stress	Generated checked	evidence	Runtime behavior
River flow	MLP/LSTM/GRU; multivariate lags; multi-step horizon	preprocessing, windowing, training, predictions, metrics, plots, logs		flood-risk alerting
Smart-home	ARIMA/SARIMA/SARIMAX; seasonality; exogenous variables	statistical pipeline, fitted model, predicted load, metrics, plots, logs		safe/alert load monitoring
Solar power	XGBoost/Prophet; lag/rolling features; hourly data	feature engineering, training, horizon-wise predictions, metrics, plots, logs		generation monitoring

executable preprocessing, training, prediction, evaluation, and visualization artifacts; (iii) produce observable execution evidence such as logs, metrics, plots, prediction files, and alerts; and (iv) connect generated predictions to application-level IoT/CPS behavior. The goal is feasibility and traceability, not forecast-model selection: the algorithms exercise the framework, but we do not claim that they are the most accurate choices.

The three cases were chosen because they differ in domain, data shape, model family, preprocessing demands, and runtime objective. River-flow forecasting uses multivariate hydrological data with MLP/LSTM/GRU models and stresses timestamp handling, missing values, feature roles, lag windows, multi-step prediction, and flood-risk alerting. Smart-home energy forecasting uses ARIMA/SARIMA/SARIMAX/ETS models and stresses seasonality, exogenous variables, statistical-model configuration, short-horizon load prediction, and safe/alert monitoring. Solar-power forecasting uses XGBoost with lag and rolling-window features, with optional Prophet, and stresses hourly data, domain-aware zero handling, feature engineering, horizon-wise evaluation, and generation monitoring. Together, the cases exercise deep-learning sequence forecasting, statistical seasonal forecasting, and feature-engineered machine-learning forecasting under the same model-to-code pipeline.

Table 1 summarizes the artifact-level evidence. The three cases do not constitute an independent benchmark, and they do not prove coverage of every possible forecasting workflow. They show that the same ML2++ metamodel and generator can express distinct forecasting regimes, generate executable artifacts, produce inspectable outputs, and bind predictions to IoT/CPS behavior. We checked successful end-to-end execution by the presence of the expected generated artifacts, logs, prediction files, metrics, and plots; we did not formally prove transformation correctness or systematically count failed runs. This supports RQ1 and RQ2 at the level of technical feasibility and reproducible artifact generation, while the user study evaluates human effort. For reproducibility, the repository includes the ML2++ model instances, generated execution artifacts, logs, prediction outputs, evaluation metrics, and visualization results for the three validation use cases: <https://github.com/micss-lab/ML-QuadratPP>.

6 The Three-Stage User Study

6.1 Participants, Tasks, and How We Read the Data

Eight participants (P1–P8) each carried one of the three forecasting use cases through all three stages. They were deliberately diverse,

Figure 2: Evaluation logic. The orange boxes (Stage 1 + Stage 2) form the *combined non-model-driven baseline*: Stage 1 covers manual Python forecasting implementation and Stage 2 covers IoT/CPS template integration. The teal box (Stage 3) is the ML2++ model-driven path. The dashed arrow marks the comparison boundary; the study asks whether Stage 3 reduces total engineering effort relative to the combined baseline.

ranging from beginners to experts in Python, time series, ML, and MDE/DSL, because we wanted to see how ML2++ behaves across realistic skill levels, not only in expert hands. Throughout the paper, *use-case knowledge* means familiarity with the assigned application area (river flow, smart-home energy, or solar energy), not a vague notion of general expertise. Table 2 gives the full profiles.

This diversity is a strength for realism but a constraint on interpretation: with eight people spread across three use cases, four model families, and a wide range of backgrounds, any pooled average would hide more than it reveals. We therefore read the data the only way it can fairly be read: *within a participant and within a use case*. The reference point for each person is their own combined baseline against their own Stage 3 result. Comparisons *between* participants are treated as context, not evidence. Where a value is approximate, we mark it rather than implying a precision we do not have, and we draw no statistical conclusions from so small a sample. This is a deliberate stance, not a disclaimer added after the fact.

6.2 Stage 1: Building It by Hand

Stage 1 establishes what code-centric development actually costs. Each participant prepared data, engineered features, configured and trained a model, evaluated it, produced plots, and debugged, covering the full manual loop. Table 3 reports the per-step minutes by use case.

The headline of Stage 1 is variance. In the river-flow group, manual effort was dominated by preprocessing, deep-learning configuration, and debugging; P2 reported an unusually high total driven by preprocessing and learning, and P6 (a beginner) spent the bulk of its time on preprocessing and debugging. In smart-home, P8’s time reflects SARIMA’s very long seasonal period (1440 lags) and repeated runtime crashes, while the beginner P4 spent most of its time on training and debugging. In solar, P5 and P7 spent most of their time configuring Prophet and XGBoost. The common thread is not which model is hardest, but that manual development scatters the engineering evidence across scripts, notebooks, and local assumptions: keeping preprocessing, training, evaluation, and runtime use mutually consistent is entirely on the developer, and it is exactly that consistency work that is hard to inspect later.

6.3 Stage 2: Making It Run as an IoT/CPS Workflow

Stage 2 captures the step that is easy to forget when comparing tools: turning the working forecasting code into something an IoT/CPS application can actually execute. This is real, recurring work, and the per-step times in Table 3 show it. Reusing the template helped: participants did not rewrite their models, but they still had to understand the template, adapt their scripts to it, and run the full pipeline. The failures here were integration failures rather than modeling failures: package-installation problems, feature-name and timestamp mismatches, scaling and lag-buffer misalignments, input-shape errors, and server configuration. In other words, Stage 2 moves the burden from *writing the algorithm* to *wiring it in*, precisely the overhead a model-driven generator is meant to remove, and precisely why the realistic baseline must include it. Manual code-size reports, available for six participants, ranged from about 90 to 500 lines (P1 ~120, P2 ~108, P4 132, P5 107, P7 90, P8 500; P3/P6 N.A.); because this was not recorded consistently, we use it only as supporting evidence of integration burden, not as a primary outcome.

6.4 Stage 3: Modeling It in ML2++

In Stage 3 the participant stops writing and wiring code and instead declares the workflow: datasets, feature roles, preprocessing, model configuration, metrics, visualization, and prediction variables. The framework generates the executable artifacts and the evidence outputs.

We now have Stage 3 data for all eight participants. Three qualifications govern how the numbers should be read, and we state them before the tables. First, Stage 3 was not conducted immediately after the manual and template-based stages: participants performed the ML2++ stage approximately 40 days after completing Stage 1 and Stage 2. This delay reduces the risk of a short-term practice effect, although it does not remove the fixed-order threat because participants had already been exposed to the use case, dataset, feature roles, horizon, and target. Second, P6’s time totals are approximate (rounded from session timing) and are marked with ~; the rest are as reported. Third, each Stage 3 total is the reported modeling-plus-review time plus the extra-learning time, so the per-step (B4)

Table 2: Participant profiles for the three-stage evaluation, compiled from questionnaire forms. Expertise columns use B = Beginner, I = Intermediate, A = Advanced, E = Expert. UC Know. = familiarity with the assigned application area (river flow / smart-home / solar); TS = time-series expertise; ML = machine-learning expertise.

P	Use Case	Educ.	Sector	Primary Role	Programming / ML			MDE / IoT		UC Know.
					Python	TS	ML	IoT/CPS	MDE	
P1	Smart-home	Master's	Industry	Softw. Architect / Full-stack	E	A	I	E	A	I
P2	River flow	Master's	Academic	Data Scientist / ML Engineer	I	I	I	B	B	I
P3	River flow	Bachelor's	Academic	Data Scientist / ML Engineer	I	I	I	B	B	I
P4	Smart-home	Bachelor's	Academic	Data Scientist / ML Engineer	B	B	B	B	B	B
P5	Solar power	Master's	Academic	Educator / Researcher	I	I	I	I	I	I
P6	River flow	Bachelor's	Academic	Master Student	B	B	B	B	B	B
P7	Solar power	Master's	Industry	Data Scientist / ML Engineer	A	A	A	A	A	I
P8	Smart-home	Bachelor's	Industry	Data Scientist / Embedded SW Eng.	A	A	A	I	I	I

Sector: *Academic* = student or researcher/educator; *Industry* = professional practitioner. Educ.: highest degree completed.

Table 3: Stage 1 (manual Python) and Stage 2 (IoT-template reuse) step times, in minutes, for all eight participants grouped by use case. "N.A." = not separately recorded; \geq marks lower bounds; "incl." = folded into the row above. P6 Stage 1 figures are lower bounds; P8's long training reflects the SARIMA seasonal period of 1440; P5's Stage 2 total is a lower bound.

Step (min)	River flow			Smart-home			Solar	
	P2	P3	P6	P1	P4	P8	P5	P7
<i>Stage 1 – Manual Python</i>								
Data preprocessing	240	180	226	20	30	60	120	30
Model configuration	60	100	23	30	30	120	240	60
Model training	60	120	5	40	100	60	30	60
Model eval./plots	60	45	5	20	50	60	15	30
Plotting/diag.	60	90	52	20	20	30	15	30
Debugging	300	incl.	≥ 60	30	70	30	≈ 100	30
Extra learning	360	N.A.	≥ 120	90	60	60	(in total)	90
Total S1	1140	540	≥ 491	250	360	420	420	330
<i>Stage 2 – IoT-Template Reuse</i>								
Understand template	N.A.	40	30	30	45	60	N.A.	40
Adapt scripts	75	30	30	120	120	60	N.A.	60
Run pipeline	60	50	N.A.	10	30	90	30	30
Total S2	135	120	60	160	195	130	≥ 30	130

figures are an *indicative* breakdown that need not sum exactly to that total, because they were recorded as separate estimates. This matters most for the beginner P4, whose per-step estimates add up to more than the session total it reported. B12 debugging time is already included in the modeling-plus-review time and is reported separately only as a diagnostic measure; it is not added again when computing the S3 total. In the three partial Stage 3 runs, the remaining gaps were at the last-mile modeling level, especially final model/server configuration or behavior/runtime binding; the study did not instrument a more detailed per-gap checklist, so these cases are treated as weaker evidence. Table 4 reports the data use case by use case.

With data for all eight participants, the questionnaires tell a consistent story about *where* the work lives once development moves into ML2++. The easier and harder elements separate clearly: data types and basic preprocessing are rated 2–3 by almost everyone, while model configuration and Things/behaviors are generally rated harder, especially in smart-home, where ports, model options, and configuration reach 4 for P4 and P8 but stay 1–2 for the advanced P1, with the river-flow and solar groups showing a similar ordering. Experience appears to explain part of the remaining difficulty more clearly than the assigned use case, although the small sample prevents causal conclusions: P1 rates the learning curve easy and

reports few errors and little debugging, whereas P4, P6, and P8 rate it harder (3–4) and report more errors and less clear messages. P4 is the extreme case: a beginner with the study's highest debugging time (300 min), difficulty 3–4 on every step, and per-step estimates that exceed its session total, so we read its numbers cautiously, but it is now a full participant rather than a gap. Finally, satisfaction is mixed but does not collapse: ratings range from 2 to 4, while code quality, maintainability, and flexibility are mostly moderate to high (3–5). Even P4 and P8 rate satisfaction at 3, suggesting that their difficulty is mainly in *getting the model right*, not in rejecting the approach.

The most informative answer, though, came from the open question of which step was hardest. Participants did not point to preprocessing or evaluation, which are the parts ML2++ automates, but to *authoring the model instance itself*: the DSL syntax, the Things, and the model/server configuration. This is the central qualitative finding of the study, and it is what makes RQ4 actionable: ML2++ does not so much remove difficulty as relocate it, from implementing and integrating code toward specifying, configuring, and understanding the model. The effort comparison in Section 7 quantifies the first half of that statement; this difficulty profile is the second half, and it points directly at where future tooling should help.

Table 4: Stage 3 (ML2++) results for all eight participants, grouped by use case. *Top*: time, completion, and per-step effort. *B4* cells give difficulty / time (difficulty 1 = very easy to 5 = very hard, time in min); *B3* C = complete, P = partial; *P6* totals approximate (~); *P4*'s per-step estimates exceed its session total, so Table 5 uses 460. *Bottom*: element difficulty, learning, debugging, and quality (*B5–B7* 1 = easy/intuitive to 5 = hard; *B9* 0–3; *B10* 1 = unclear to 5 = clear; *B11* 1 = easy to 5 = hard; *B12* min and is included in modeling-plus-review time, not added separately; *B13–B15* 1 = poor to 5 = excellent; *C1* 1 = very dissatisfied to 5 = very satisfied).

Item	River flow			Smart-home			Solar	
	P2	P3	P6	P1	P4	P8	P5	P7
<i>B1 – Time & effort (min)</i>								
Modeling + review	60	105	~156	200	400	200	40	420
Extra learning	45	45	~45	60	60	120	(in tot.)	60
S3 total	105	150	~201	260	460	320	40	480
B2 – DSL lines	158	156	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	150	150	170
B3 – Completion	C	C	P	C	P	P	C	C
<i>B4 – Workflow step (difficulty/time, min)</i>								
PP Data preprocessing	4 / 5	3 / 10	4 / 40	2 / 8	4 / 100	4 / 45	3 / 5	3 / 60
MC Model config.	4 / 20	2 / 70	4 / 25	3 / 10	4 / 200	4 / 60	3 / 15	4 / 120
TR Model training	2 / 5	2 / 10	3 / 20	2 / 12	4 / 200	3 / 60	3 / 5	4 / 90
EV Model evaluation	2 / 5	1 / 15	3 / 10	4 / 20	4 / 100	4 / 30	3 / 5	4 / 90
<i>B5 – Element difficulty</i>								
DT Data types & objects	3	2	3	2	2	3	3	3
TB Things & behaviors	3	2	3	3	3	4	3	4
Pt Ports & properties	3	2	3	1	3	4	N.A.	3
MO Model options	3	2	2	2	4	4	2	4
Cf Configuration	3	2	2	3	4	4	2	4
<i>B6–B7 – Learning & usability</i>								
B6 Learning curve	4	3	3	2	4	4	3	3
B7 Intuitiveness	3	3	3	3	4	4	4	4
<i>B9–B12 – Debugging & error handling</i>								
B9 Error frequency	2	2	3	1	3	2	2	2
B10 Error clarity	4	2	2	3	3	2	1	3
B11 Debug effort	2	2	4	3	3	4	4	3
B12 Debug time (min)	15	20	20	25	300	60	6	60
<i>B13–B15 – Quality, maintainability, flexibility</i>								
B13 Code quality	3	4	3	3	3	4	4	4
B14 Maintainability	4	3	3	3	2	4	4	5
B15 Flexibility	4	4	3	2	4	3	4	4
<i>C1 – Overall assessment</i>								
C1 Satisfaction	2	3	2	3	3	3	3	4

7 Does ML2++ Reduce Effort?

7.1 The Comparison, and How It Is Built

The effort question (RQ3) comes down to one comparison: each participant's Stage 3 time against their own combined baseline, Stage 1 + Stage 2. Table 5 reports it for all eight participants. Every figure in that table is taken directly from the tables that precede it, with no separate bookkeeping: the Stage 1 and Stage 2 totals come from Table 3, and the Stage 3 totals are the S3 totals of the Stage 3 use-case tables, namely 260, 105, 150, 460, 40, ~201, 480, and 320 minutes for P1 through P8. The *Change* column is Stage 3 minus baseline, so a negative number means ML2++ took less visible effort. Lower-bound and approximate values are marked with \geq and \sim so the reader always knows how solid each cell is.

7.2 Reading the Result

Of the five participants who *completed* the Stage-3 task, P1, P2, P3, P5, and P7, four took less time in the ML2++ stage than in their combined baseline and one (P7) took about 20 minutes more. The three participants whose Stage-3 run was only *partial*, P4, P6, and P8, also recorded lower times, but an unfinished task naturally takes less time, so we report them separately and do not treat them as clean reductions (the *Compl.* column of Table 5). All of this is read cautiously for a further reason: the stages were always performed in the order Stage 1 \rightarrow Stage 2 \rightarrow Stage 3, so by the ML2++ stage a

participant had already solved the same forecasting problem twice and knew the data, features, horizon, and target. However, Stage 3 was performed approximately 40 days after Stage 1 and Stage 2 rather than immediately afterwards. This delay makes a purely short-term practice effect less likely, but prior task exposure may still have contributed to the lower Stage 3 times. Hence, we say “less time in the ML2++ stage” rather than “faster” (Section 10).

Because the use cases are not interchangeable, the honest reading is use-case by use case. Among the completers: in **river flow**, P2 and P3 both took less time than they did by hand, though P2's very high Stage 1 total makes its change (-1170 min) an outlier that should not be over-read, while P3 still shows a large reduction (-510). In **smart-home**, the completer P1 took less time (-150). In **solar**, P5 shows a clear reduction, although its very low Stage 3 total (40 min) is itself a value to treat cautiously, while P7 is the single completer whose Stage 3 cost slightly more (+20), because the modeling task still demanded heavy model and workflow configuration. The three partial runs (P4 -95 , P8 -230 , P6 ≤ -350) point the same way but, being unfinished, are weaker evidence. The fair summary is measured, not triumphant: among participants who finished the task, the ML2++ stage usually took less time, by amounts that depend heavily on the manual baseline, the model family, and how much was already learned in the earlier stages.

Table 5: Effort comparison between the combined baseline (Stage 1 + Stage 2) and Stage 3 ML2++, in minutes. Totals are derived from Tables 3 and 4; Change = Stage 3 minus Baseline (negative = less time in the ML2++ stage). Compl. is Stage-3 task completion (C = complete, P = partial). \geq = lower bound, \sim = approximate. P2 (very high baseline) and P5 (very low Stage 3) are outliers. The three partial Stage-3 runs (P4, P6, P8) naturally take less time than a fully completed task, so their negative changes are not clean reductions and are read separately in the text. Stage-1/2 completion was not separately recorded.

P	Use Case	Model Family	Compl.	S1	S2	Baseline	S3	Change
P1	Smart-home	SARIMA / SARIMAX	C	250	160	410	260	-150
P2	River flow	LSTM / GRU	C	1140	135	1275	105	-1170
P3	River flow	LSTM / GRU	C	540	120	660	150	-510
P4	Smart-home	SARIMA / Holt-Winters	P	360	195	555	460	-95
P5	Solar power	Prophet / XGBoost	C	420	≥ 30	≥ 450	40	≤ -410
P6	River flow	LSTM / GRU	P	≥ 491	60	≥ 551	~ 201	≤ -350
P7	Solar power	Prophet / XGBoost	C	330	130	460	480	+20
P8	Smart-home	SARIMA / SARIMAX	P	420	130	550	320	-230

7.3 Why the Effort Moves, Not Just Shrinks

The reductions are not magic automation; they are a redistribution. ML2++ removes the repeated pipeline construction of Stage 1 and the integration work of Stage 2, but it adds the cost of specifying the model correctly. The exploratory pattern in the data supports this: manual effort tracks prior Python, forecasting, and use-case knowledge, whereas Stage 3 effort tracks the difficulty of the modeling elements themselves, which is exactly why the one increase (P7) and the hardest beginner (P4) both spend their Stage 3 time on model and configuration rather than on data handling. Participants' own comments close the loop: several said that writing a complete, correct model instance was the demanding part, especially for those new to the DSL or the forecasting task. So the framework does not make the hard decisions disappear; it makes them explicit and inspectable, and concentrates them at the model-authoring step.

7.4 Answers to the Research Questions

Bringing the two halves of the evaluation together: RQ1 and RQ2 are supported by the artifact-based technical validation (Section 5), as feasibility rather than independent benchmark evidence: ML2++ expressed three distinct forecasting workflows, generated executable artifacts, produced inspectable evidence outputs, and connected predictions to runtime behavior. RQ3 is answered descriptively here: of the five participants who completed the Stage-3 task, four took less time than their combined Stage 1 + Stage 2 baseline and one (P7) took about 20 min more; the three partial completions (P4, P6, P8) also recorded lower times but are not directly comparable. We read even this cautiously given the fixed stage order (Section 10). RQ4 is answered by the difficulty profile of Section 6 together with this comparison: the effort that remains is concentrated in model configuration, DSL understanding, and, most pointedly, authoring the model instance. The first three RQs say the framework works and tends to save effort; RQ4 says where the next improvement must come from, which is the thread we pick up in the discussion.

8 A Second Lens: the Graphical Editor

The three-stage study tells us about the textual modeling path. But ML2++ has two front-ends onto the same metamodel, and a fair account of the framework has to say something about the graphical one. We do this through a separate, complementary study, namely

Table 6: Graphical-editor study: quantitative measurements. Time in hours; LoC = lines of code. Each cell lists the four individual participant observations (sorted). ML2++ generates code, so its LoC is ≈ 0 . Errors and debugging time are totals across all three use cases; familiarity is time to become familiar with the tool.

Metric	ML2 (Group A)	ML2++ (Group B)
Design time (h)	0.3, 0.5, 0.6, 1.2	0.75, 1.0, 1.0, 2.5 [†]
Implementation time (h)	1.5, 2.5, 3.0, 3.25	2.5, 3.0, 3.5, 5.5 [†]
DSL / model LoC	160, 200, 245, N.A.	≈ 0 (generated)
Manual Python LoC	20, 25, 30, 60	0 (generated)
Errors encountered	8, 15, 20, 25	4, 8, 10, 12
Debugging time (h)	1, 2, 2, 4	0.1, 0.5, 0.5
Familiarity time (h)	1, 2, 2.5, 4	1.0, 1.2, 1.4, 2.4

[†]ML2++ includes one outlier participant; excluding the outlier gives comparable times to ML2. ML2 participants can copy-paste code across use cases; ML2++ participants cannot, partly explaining higher implementation time. ML2++ debugging time was separately recorded for three of the four participants, and one ML2 DSL-LoC value was not recorded ("N.A.").

Smet's [18] comparative usability evaluation (a master's thesis) of the offline textual ML2/ML-Quadrat environment (Group A, $n = 4$) against the web-based graphical ML2++ Sirius-Web environment (Group B, $n = 4$), run on three use cases: Stress Watch, Soil Moisture, and Server Prediction, with the two groups balanced on education, role, and IoT/MDE/ML experience. Group A and Group B participants are disjoint from P1–P8 of the staged study.

We are explicit that this evidence is *complementary, not interchangeable* with the staged study. It compares textual ML2 against graphical ML2++ on classical ML-enabled IoT/CPS tasks, whereas Sections 6–7 compare manual, template, and textual ML2++ development on forecasting tasks. The two studies therefore answer different questions, and we read the graphical results as a usability lens on the second editor modality rather than as a second effort measurement of the same workflow. Table 6 reports the quantitative measurements; the qualitative percentages are summarized in the text to keep the paper within the page limit.

8.1 Where Graphical ML2++ Clearly Helps

The strongest and least ambiguous effect is on the *amount of handwritten artifact and the failure it invites*. ML2 participants wrote 160–245 lines of DSL plus 20–60 lines of manual Python; ML2++ participants wrote essentially none, since the code is generated.

That difference shows up downstream: ML2 users hit 8–25 errors, mostly syntactic, and spent one to four hours debugging, while ML2++ users hit 4–12 errors and spent under 0.6 hours. The configuration concern that was hardest in ML2, DAML, improved markedly under the graphical editor (from 75% of participants rating it “hard” to 25%), and overall satisfaction rose from 25% to 75%. The form-based abstraction, in participants’ own words, made the analytics configuration intuitive rather than fiddly. This is the same lesson as the textual study seen from another angle: take the syntax burden away and the obvious sources of friction fall with it.

8.2 Where It Does Not, and Why That Matters

What the graphical editor does *not* do is make everything faster. Once the single outlier participant is set aside and ML2’s ability to copy-paste code across use cases is accounted for, raw design and implementation times are comparable between the two; we therefore do not claim a graphical speed-up in raw modeling time. Two difficulties also survived the move to graphical modeling. Behavior modeling, especially the state-machine logic, was rated equally or *more* difficult in ML2++, with participants finding the executable behavior disorganized in the graphical view. And error-message clarity and debugging effort were judged about equally poor in both groups, which is unsurprising: the two editors sit on the same underlying compiler, so they inherit the same diagnostics. These are not incidental gripes; they name the parts of the toolchain that abstraction alone does not fix.

8.3 What the Two Studies Agree On

Read together, the staged and graphical studies converge on one message. Both show that ML2++ removes a large, concrete burden: hand-written pipeline and integration code in the staged study, and hand-written DSL and Python in the graphical study. Both show that the remaining difficulty clusters in the same places: configuring and authoring the model, modeling behavior, and making sense of compiler feedback. The graphical editor improves the experience of the first of these without yet resolving the others, which sharpens the same improvement agenda the textual study produced: clearer error messages, better behavior-modeling support, richer documentation, and more worked examples.

9 Discussion

Three lessons emerge once the technical validation and the two user studies are read together.

First, ML2++ works across genuinely different forecasting workflows. The artifact-based validation does more than list three examples: it applies the same criteria to deep-learning river-flow, statistical seasonal smart-home, and feature-engineered solar forecasting. In each case, the model instance generated runnable artifacts, produced logs/metrics/plots/predictions, and connected predictions to application behavior. This is still feasibility evidence, not an independent benchmark, but it is evidence for a *class* of workflows rather than a single demonstration.

Second, modeling tends to cost less than building by hand, but the claim has to stay modest. The fair comparison is against a baseline that includes both the forecasting code and the IoT integration a non-model-driven developer would still write. Against that baseline,

four of the five participants who completed the Stage-3 task took less time, with one small increase (P7); the three partial completions (P4, P6, P8) also recorded lower times but, being unfinished, are reported separately. We treat this as a consistent direction in a small, heterogeneous sample rather than a measured speed-up. Two cells (P2’s high baseline, P5’s low Stage 3) are outliers, and, because the stages ran in fixed order, the Stage 3 figures may partly reflect familiarity gained earlier. The approximately 40-day gap before Stage 3 reduces the risk of a short-term practice effect, but it cannot eliminate the broader order effect. The honest headline is therefore “usually less time in the ML2++ stage, by amounts that depend on the manual baseline, the model family, and prior exposure,” not “faster.”

Third, and most usefully, ML2++ changes where the difficulty lives. This is the finding that ties the whole paper together. Across both studies, the framework removes a large, concrete burden (pipeline and integration code in the staged study; hand-written DSL and Python in the graphical study), and in both the residual difficulty lands in the same place: configuring and *authoring the model instance*, modeling behavior, and interpreting compiler feedback. The graphical editor eases the first of these. Form-based DAML configuration was clearly more usable, with fewer errors and higher satisfaction, without yet resolving behavior modeling or diagnostics, which both editors inherit from a shared compiler.

For verification and validation, the takeaway is that such a tool is best judged as an *evidence chain*, model → validation feedback → generated code → predictions → metrics → plots → logs → runtime bindings, not as a code generator alone. ML2++ makes that chain explicit and inspectable; we assess its benefit only indirectly here, through effort and difficulty rather than defect detection, which motivates the direction in Section 11.

10 Threats to Validity

We read this study as exploratory, and the threats below are the reason.

Construct validity. Our main effort measure is self-reported visible time, which can fold in learning, waiting, repeated execution, and pauses that were not always separated consistently. Time is also only a proxy for “engineering effort,” and a coarse one; it says nothing directly about correctness or maintainability, which we capture only through perception items. The per-step (B4) breakdowns are indicative and do not always sum to the reported session totals, most visibly for the beginner P4, so we rely on the session totals for the effort comparison and read the per-step figures only as relative difficulty signals. The baselines also include one-time “extra learning” time that the Stage-3 figures do not match in size, which can inflate the apparent difference.

Deliverable equivalence and correctness. We controlled functional targets by using the same use-case checklist within each participant’s task (features, lag/horizon, metrics, plots, and alert/monitoring binding), but we did not run a formal equivalence test on forecast quality or output similarity across stages. This is deliberate because forecast accuracy is out of scope, yet it means the effort comparison is about reaching the same engineering target, not proving predictive equivalence. We also did not collect objective defect counts,

failed-run counts, or telemetry, so the evidence chain is validated at feasibility level rather than as a formal correctness assessment.

Ordering and practice effects. Participants always worked in the fixed order Stage 1 → Stage 2 → Stage 3, with no counterbalancing. By the time they reached the ML2++ stage they had already built the same forecasting workflow twice and knew the dataset, feature roles, horizon, and target, so part of the Stage 3 time reduction may reflect prior task exposure rather than the tool alone. However, Stage 3 was not conducted immediately after the earlier stages: participants performed the ML2++ stage approximately 40 days after completing Stage 1 and Stage 2. This temporal gap reduces the likelihood of a purely short-term practice effect, because participants were less likely to remember all implementation details from the manual and template-based stages. Nevertheless, it does not fully eliminate the order effect, since participants had already been exposed to the task and its modeling requirements. We therefore describe the result as lower time *in the ML2++ stage* rather than as a causal speed-up; a counterbalanced or between-subjects design is needed to separate tool effect from order.

Experimenter bias. The evaluation was run by the framework's authors and the timings are self-reported within a single session, which can introduce demand characteristics and optimistic recording. An independent, instrumented replication would strengthen the evidence.

Internal validity and data quality. Although we now have data for all eight participants, two cells are extreme and are flagged as such: P2's very high Stage 1 total, which dominates its change figure, and P5's very low Stage 3 total. P6's time totals are approximate, and P5's Stage 2 total is a lower bound. We handle these by marking approximate and lower-bound values explicitly rather than smoothing them, by flagging the outliers in the text, and by applying no statistical test to so small a sample. A further asymmetry is completion: three Stage-3 runs (P4, P6, P8) were only partial, and since an unfinished task takes less time we exclude them from the clean effort comparison and report them separately; Stage-1/2 completion was not recorded. These choices limit what we claim but keep the claims defensible.

External validity. Eight participants, three use cases, and a fixed set of model families cannot support generalization. The graphical-editor study is complementary rather than equivalent: it compares textual ML2 with graphical ML2++ on classical ML-enabled tasks, not on the forecasting tasks of the staged study, so its results inform the second editor modality but do not transfer one-to-one.

Conclusion validity. Because of the above, we draw qualitative, within-participant, use-case-level conclusions and avoid pooled averages or significance claims. The direction of the effort change, four of five completed-task reductions, with the three partial runs read separately, is suggestive, not confirmatory. These limitations are precisely why a larger, more controlled study is the immediate next step rather than a distant one, as discussed next.

11 Future Work and Conclusion

The study points to four immediate next steps. First, the effort results need a larger, instrumented replication, ideally with about

forty participants on one shared use case, telemetry or screen-recorded timing, explicit failed-run counts, and a completion checklist for each deliverable. Second, the strongest residual difficulty is model-instance authoring. This aligns with recent LLM work showing that instance models can often be drafted, but rarely produced validly without additional structure or checking [4, 15]. We therefore plan a review-in-the-loop workflow in which users describe a forecasting scenario in structured natural language, receive an initial ML2++ model instance, and validate it before generation. Third, both studies name the same toolchain improvements: clearer compiler diagnostics, better state-machine support, richer documentation, worked examples, and stronger runtime feedback. Fourth, we will add change tasks and tool baselines: evolving an existing model, adding a feature or metric, and comparing ML2++ with low-code/MLOps routes such as Node-RED/StreamPipes plus MLflow/Kubeflow/TFX-style tracking and orchestration.

ML2++ is an existing model-driven framework introduced in prior work; this paper contributes evidence about whether it earns its place in practice. The artifact-based technical validation showed that ML2++ can express three different forecasting-enabled IoT/CPS workflows, generate runnable artifacts, produce inspectable evidence, and bind predictions to application behavior. The staged study showed that, against a realistic baseline of manual forecasting plus IoT integration, the ML2++ stage took less time for four of the five participants who completed the task, while three partial runs are reported separately and the result remains descriptive because of the small sample and fixed order. The graphical study showed that Sirius-Web reduces hand-written code, errors, and debugging and improves satisfaction, although it does not yet solve behavior modeling or diagnostics. Overall, ML2++ does not remove the hard parts of forecasting-enabled IoT/CPS engineering; it relocates them from coding and integration toward explicit, inspectable model authoring. The generated artifacts are ordinary scripts, logs, plots, and result files, so they can be exposed to MLOps systems for tracking and deployment, although native MLflow/Kubeflow/TFX integration is not yet implemented. The full artifacts, including model instances, generated code, and execution logs, are available at <https://github.com/micss-lab/ML-QuadratPP>; a replication package will add the anonymized study data, figure scripts, and a README that separates technical validation from empirical evaluation.

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